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**Deep learning methods for satellites compressive
imaging**

- The research presented was done in the scope of the EU-funded project:
- **“SUper-Resolved comPRessive InStrument in the visible and medium infrared for Earth observation applications” – SURPRISE**
- **Objective:** constructing a class of innovative **satellite imaging** sensors with **enhanced** capabilities in terms of onboard **data processing**, **spatial resolution**, and **encryption functionalities**.

Schematic diagram of the optical section of the SURPRISE demonstrator

Compressive Sensing

SURPRISE sensors acquire images using **Compressive**

Sensing:

- The signal in a **compressed form** by generalizing the concept of **sampling**
- The signal is sensed by a **matrix Φ** with **(i.i.d.)** random weights

$$y = \Phi x$$

with $y \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times 1}$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ and $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $m \ll n$.

- x needs to be **sparse** or **compressible** in some basis
- Problem: How to reconstruct original image x starting from y ?

Inverse problems in imaging

- Traditional **approach** to inverse problems:
- Make the ill-posed problem **well-posed** with some **assumptions** on how the original image should look like
- Solve an **optimization problem** that looks for the original image that:
 - **matches** well the **observations** when passed through the forward model
 - **fits** the **assumptions** made on what it should be

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{x}} \underbrace{\|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\|_2^2}_{\text{data fidelity}} + \underbrace{\lambda R(\mathbf{x})}_{\text{regularization}}$$

This cost encodes our knowledge of how the original image should be. Example: Total Variation for natural images

- Particularly useful for natural images with **compressible gradients**,
 - i.e. most of the energy is packed in very few of the image gradients

$$\hat{X} = \arg \min_X \text{TV}(X) + \lambda \|y - \Phi x\|_2^2$$

- X is a two-dimensional image
- x is the vectorized version X

- **Total variation** $\text{TV}(X) = \sum_{i,j} \sqrt{|X_{i+1,j} - X_{i,j}|^2 + |X_{i,j+1} - X_{i,j}|^2}$

Inverse problems in imaging

- **Deep Learning** approach:
 - directly **learn** the reconstruction **function** using supervision of ground truth original images
 - a neural network produces an **estimate** of the **original image** from the observed image

Deep Learning for inverse problems in imaging

Performance comparison between traditional reconstruction algorithms (blue) and the deep learning based ones (green, red) [1].

[1] W. Shi, F. Jiang, S. Liu e D. Zhao, «Scalable Convolutional Neural Network for Image Compressed Sensing,» in CVPR, Long Beach, 2019.

ISTA-Net Algorithm [1]

- The **ISTA-Net** framework consists of **mapping** the classic Iterative Shrinkage/Thresholding Algorithm (**ISTA**) into a **DNN**.
- The **architecture** is made up of a fixed number of **steps** that correspond to **iterations** in the traditional algorithm.

$$r^{(k)} = x^{(k-1)} - \rho^{(k)} \Phi^{(T)} (\Phi x^{(k-1)} - y)$$

$$x^{(k)} = \operatorname{argmin}_x \frac{1}{2} \|x - r^{(k)}\|_2^2 + \lambda \|F(x)\|_1$$

[1] J. Zhang e B. Ghanem, «ISTA-Net: Interpretable Optimization-Inspired Deep Network for Image Compressive Sensing,» in 2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2018.

ISTA-Net Algorithm

- $\mathcal{F}^{(k)}$ - Forward Transform
 - two linear convolutional operators + ReLU
- $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}^{(k)}$ - Backward
 - Symmetric to $\mathcal{F}^{(k)}$.
- N_f denotes the number of feature maps.

We employed (a subset of) the **DFC2020 dataset**

- Published for IEEE GRSS Data Fusion Contest 2020
- **Sentinel-2 images with 12 spectral channels** and GSD up to 10 m
- Very good scene variability
- 5178 images having size 256x256
 - ✓ Training set: 5128 images, test set 50 images

Dataset – sample images

- Comparison performance of ISTA-net on a test set of 7 images

	ISTA-NET				TV			
	25%	50%	75%	100%	25%	50%	75%	100%
botticino	37.94	40.25	43.23	69.54	32.50	35.50	35.52	35.58
foglioline	19.79	23.23	27.34	69.10	17.76	20.38	20.54	23.20
legno	29.06	30.51	33.11	70.10	27.54	28.86	29.04	29.18
prato	24.30	28.55	33.12	70.79	19.67	23.88	23.94	27.27
sassolini	28.11	32.32	36.78	69.47	22.18	27.57	27.74	29.52
tombino	24.36	27.60	31.43	69.32	20.93	24.49	24.57	26.43
travertino	29.50	31.06	33.63	69.97	28.42	29.34	29.45	29.63
AVERAGE	27.58	30.50	34.09	69.76	24.14	27.15	27.26	28.69

Reconstruction results in terms of PSNR (dB) for 32x32 super-resolution factor

Convolutional Image Reconstruction

- **Problem:** The **SURPRISE** instruments **senses blocks** of pixels separately

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_{i1}^{P1} \\ y_{i2}^{P1} \\ y_{i1}^{P1} \\ y_{i2}^{P2} \\ y_{i1}^{P2} \\ y_{i2}^{P2} \\ y_{i1}^{P2} \\ y_{i2}^{P3} \\ y_{i1}^{P3} \\ y_{i2}^{P3} \\ y_{i3}^{P3} \\ y_{i1}^{P4} \\ y_{i2}^{P4} \\ y_{i3}^{P4} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta & \beta & \alpha & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \alpha & \beta & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \beta & \beta & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \alpha & \beta & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \beta & \beta & \alpha \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \alpha & \beta \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \beta & \alpha & \beta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{i1}^{P1} \\ x_{i2}^{P1} \\ x_{i3}^{P1} \\ x_{i4}^{P1} \\ x_{i1}^{P2} \\ x_{i2}^{P2} \\ x_{i3}^{P2} \\ x_{i4}^{P2} \\ x_{i1}^{P3} \\ x_{i2}^{P3} \\ x_{i3}^{P3} \\ x_{i4}^{P3} \\ x_{i1}^{P4} \\ x_{i2}^{P4} \\ x_{i3}^{P4} \\ x_{i4}^{P4} \end{bmatrix}$$

- Also **reconstruction** was done indepently on each block,
 - This results in **discontinuities** on the borders of the **blocks**.

- **ISTA-Net** is a fully-convolutional network
 - The input fed to the network can be of **any size**
- Network was **re-trained** using inputs and labels corresponding to **multiple blocks**.
 - For memory reasons we limited ourselves to **2x2 blocks**
- Careful **simulation** of the **sensing process** which acts **independently for each block** is needed for the residual computation in the network stages.

Convolutional Image Reconstruction

- Training on dataset obtained from **DFC2020** [1] dataset
- 51280 patches of size 64x64 (2x2 blocks of 32x32 micropixels)

		RMSE	
		Independent reconstruction	Convolutional reconstruction
CR	25%	74.69	72.87
	50%	47.78	47.04
	75%	29.36	28.73

Convolutional Image Reconstruction

Independent reconstruction. Sensing matrix 32×32 , CR 25%. Notice the blocking artifacts

Convolutional Image Reconstruction

Convolutional reconstruction. Sensing matrix 32×32 , CR 25%. Notice that the blocking artifacts have been significantly suppressed.

- For each **spectral band** of the same image is a treated as a **different capture** which and reconstructed separately
- The correlation between the different **spectral bands** is not taken advantage of.
- **ISTA-Net** was modified to use spectral channels as **feature channels**.
 - Achieved by training a **weight matrix** applied along the channel dimension
 - Increase in parameters is negligible.

		RMSE	
		Single band reconstruction	Multi-band reconstruction
CR	25%	72.87	65.74
	50%	47.04	42.43
	75%	28.73	26.64

Single band reconstruction vs. multi band reconstruction (RMSE)

Reconstruction accuracy in the presence of noise

- Sensing process affected by **noise** which can be modelled according to the **following distribution**:

$$z = \Phi x + \eta = y + \eta, \eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, ay + b)$$

- Is the heteroskedastic normal approximation of a **Poisson-Gaussian noise**
- We simulate a purely signal dependent noise $\eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, ay)$ on the DFC2020 datasets and to **re-train ISTANET** on the noisy measurements.
- Three levels of noise were simulated: $SNR_z = 50, 75, 100$ [dB].
- SNR_z was obtained with the following equation:

$$SNR_z = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\sum_i y^2(i)}{\sum_j \eta^2(j)}$$

Reconstruction accuracy in the presence of noise

- Comparison between **Linear Reconstruction** and **Istanet** for various levels of compression and SNR for the signal-dependent noise

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)								
	Compression Ratio 25.00%		Compression Ratio 50.00%		Compression Ratio 75.00%		Compression Ratio 100.00%	
SNR_z [dB]	Linear Recon.	ISTANET	Linear Recon.	ISTANET	Linear Recon.	ISTANET	Linear Recon.	ISTANET
50	90.06	81.14	78.81	64.50	74.56	60.39	72.27	58.08
75	79.47	71.84	51.58	48.54	31.70	29.39	16.94	15.07
100	79.06	74.07	51.33	47.49	30.36	28.47	5.52	5.51
Noiseless	79.00	72.90	51.30	47.00	30.50	28.70	0.59	0.59

Reconstruction accuracy in the presence of noise

- Performance Comparison **50 dB of SNR and SNR 25 dB**

Ground Truth

Linear Reconstruction

ISTANET

Reconstruction accuracy in the presence of noise

- Comparison in reconstruction performance between signal-dependent and signal-independent noise

Root Mean squared Error (RMSE)									
		CR = 25.00%		CR = 50.00%		CR = 75.00%		CR = 100.00%	
SNR_z [dB]	Algorithm	Noise a_y	Noise b	Noise a_y	Noise b	Noise a_y	Noise b	Noise a_y	Noise b
50 dB	Linear Recon.	90.06	94.83	78.81	74.93	74.56	75.65	72.27	67.42
	ISTANET	81.14	88.15	64.50	64.33	60.39	60.64	58.08	56.32
75 dB	Linear Recon.	79.47	79.38	51.58	51.58	31.70	30.97	16.94	14.73
	ISTANET	71.84	73.08	48.54	47.61	29.39	29.14	15.07	13.95
100 dB	Linear Recon.	79.06	79.15	51.33	51.33	30.36	30.36	5.52	4.72
	ISTANET	74.07	73.89	47.49	48.37	28.47	28.38	5.51	4.73

- Developed several improvement version of the **state-of-the-art** deep learning algorithm for **CS reconstruction**, destined to be used for **compressive satellite imaging**.
- We demonstrate that a data-driven algorithm are **viable solution** to obtain a **high-resolution** version of a satellite image, taking into consideration some of the effects related to a **real-world scenario**.